

1 **Liposome-encapsulated Bacteriophages for Enhanced Oral Phage Therapy against *Salmonella***

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20 **ABSTRACT (maximum 250 words)**

21 Herein we report that encapsulation of bacteriophages UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 and UAB_Phi87 in
22 liposomes enhances their efficacy against *Salmonella*. The liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages had a mean
23 diameter comprising between 309 and 326 nm and a positive charge from +31.6 and +35.1 mV, depending on
24 the bacteriophage, and when stored at 4°C, they were stable for at least 3 months. *In vitro* studies
25 demonstrated that in simulated gastric fluid (pH 2.8) the titer of bacteriophages suffered a decrease of 5.7 to
26 7.8 log units, depending on the bacteriophage, while those encapsulated were significantly more stable with
27 losses comprised between 3.7 to 5.4 log units thereby confirming the protective effect of the lipid coating.
28 The liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages significantly persisted for 72 h in the 38.1% of non-infected
29 commercial broilers (*Gallus gallus*; Ross strain) whereas the non-encapsulated only persisted in the 9.5% of
30 animals. Experiments performed in animals experimentally infected with *Salmonella*, revealed that the two
31 cocktails administered daily for 6 days post-infection similarly protected the chickens against *Salmonella*
32 colonization. However, once bacteriophage treatment was stopped, the protection of the non-encapsulated
33 bacteriophages disappeared after 72 hours, while persisted at least for 1 week when the encapsulated
34 bacteriophages were administered. In addition, it was also demonstrated in in vitro experiments that the
35 cecum content of broilers is able to promote the release of bacteriophages from liposomes with different
36 kinetics for each bacteriophage. Liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages herein presented can be obtained for
37 bacteriophages with different morphology, could be easy to add to drinking water and animal feed, and could
38 be safely stored long-term in lyophilized form.

39

40 INTRODUCTION

41 Food-borne diseases are a global health problem. They include non-typhoidal *Salmonella* infection,
42 which is among the most common zoonotic pathogens that affect humans. In fact, this bacterium
43 was responsible for more than 1 million annual cases of food-related illnesses in the USA from 2000
44 to 2008 (1) and for more than 90,000 cases of salmonellosis (mainly, from *Salmonella enterica*
45 serovars Enteritidis and Typhimurium) diagnosed in the European Union (EU) in 2012 (2). The
46 major source of *Salmonella* infections in humans is poultry products (2) and poultry is the major
47 reservoir of this bacterium. The health risk is exacerbated in the case of broilers, which are
48 asymptomatic carriers that house *Salmonella* in their gut. In fact, several *Salmonella* strains colonize
49 the chickens in a persistent way without causing any signs of illness (3). This lack of clinical
50 symptoms facilitates the dissemination of *Salmonella* within flocks (4), consequently increasing the
51 probability of cross-contamination during the transport, slaughtering and processing of broilers.
52 *Salmonella* infection in broilers has been controlled mainly through the use of vaccines (5, 6),
53 probiotics, prebiotics, synbiotics (7) and antibiotics (8), although these treatments have a limited
54 effectiveness: for example, antibiotics can ultimately increase the severity and frequency of
55 colonization by some resistant *Salmonella* strains (9).

56 Bacteriophage therapy has recently been proposed for use in controlling *Salmonella* infection in
57 chickens. Bacteriophages are bacterial viruses that infect the host bacterium to subsequently
58 replicate inside of and rapidly kill the host (10). Several studies have shown that bacteriophages
59 effectively reduce *Salmonella enterica* colonization in poultry (11-15). Other researchers have
60 demonstrated that bacteriophages can be useful for food preservation and safety (16-21). Our group
61 has previously reported that a bacteriophage cocktail containing the bacteriophages UAB_Phi20,
62 UAB_Phi78 and UAB_Phi87 is highly effective at reducing *Salmonella* colonization in an
63 experimental model of *Gallus gallus* that is free of specific pathogens, and in diverse foodstuffs (20,

64 21). Despite the aforementioned advances, there remain inherent challenges in the practical use of
65 oral bacteriophage therapy. For example, bacteriophages typically lack stability in the extremely
66 acidic environment (22) as it is the pH of the stomach and exhibit a very short residence time in the
67 intestinal tract (20). These issues translate to low efficiency, which can only be compensated for by
68 very frequent treatment administration, which is costly and time-consuming (20). Thus, practical use
69 of bacteriophages for controlling *Salmonella* in broilers will require bacteriophages (or formulations
70 thereof) that are more stable to acid and that have longer residence times. Two strategies have
71 recently been developed for stabilizing bacteriophages in acidic media: addition of antacids (*e.g.*
72 CaCO_3) to the bacteriophage suspensions (15); and encapsulation of bacteriophages into polymeric
73 microcapsules, including those comprising alginate/pectin (23) (size: 1 mm), alginate/chitosan (size:
74 $780\ \mu\text{m}$) (24), methacrylate (25) and alginate/ CaCO_3 (size: $900\ \mu\text{m}$) (26). However, to date, no study
75 has reported a method which allows simultaneously an increase of stability in acid environment and
76 of the intestinal residence time of the bacteriophages in order to achieve higher reduction of
77 *Salmonella* infection in broilers. In this sense, we hypothesized that the liposomes should have two
78 primary functions: they serve as a barrier to protons (27), thereby protecting bacteriophages against
79 gastric acids; and, owing to their positively charged surface, they exhibit mucoadhesive properties
80 (28, 29) that enable a longer intestinal residence time than that observed for the corresponding non-
81 encapsulated bacteriophages. We chose cationic liposomes as the encapsulation matrix because they
82 are sub-microscale systems that are highly amenable to encapsulation of negatively-charged
83 nanoscale biological entities (30, 31) such as bacteriophages. Furthermore, cationic liposomes favor
84 dispersion of such biomolecules in aqueous media for prolonged periods, facilitate oral
85 administration of these biomolecules to animals and are degraded upon contact with intestinal bile
86 salts (32). In the work reported here, we separately encapsulated the three bacteriophages
87 (UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 or UAB_Ph87) in cationic lipid envelopes (liposomes), and then

88 compared the performance of the resulting liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages to the
89 corresponding non-encapsulated ones as orally administered bacteriophage therapy in broilers.

90

91 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

92 **Bacterial strains and growth conditions.**

93 *Salmonella* Typhimurium LB5000 (SGSC181; University of Calgary) was used for the propagation
94 of bacteriophages UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 and UAB_Phi87, and the strain *S. Typhimurium*
95 ATCC14028 Rif^R was used for the colonization of animals. All bacterial strains were grown in
96 Luria-Bertani (LB) broth or on LB agar plates for 18 h at 37°C. Viable counts of *S. Typhimurium*
97 ATCC14028 Rif^R were also determined by plating on xylose lysine deoxycholate plates (XLD,
98 Laboratorios Conda, Spain), supplemented with rifampicin (75 µg/ml) and incubated at 37°C for 18
99 h.

100 ***In vitro* multiplication of bacteriophages.**

101 UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 and UAB_Phi87 bacteriophage lysates were obtained by infecting
102 exponential cultures of LB5000 strain grown in LB broth at a multiplicity of infection (MOI; ratio of
103 infective bacteriophages to number of viable bacterial cells) of 0.01 PFU/CFU, followed by
104 incubation at 37°C for 5 h (33). After centrifugation of the cultures (10,414 X g for 10 min), the
105 supernatant was collected, and then filtered through syringe polyestersulfone (PES) filters
106 (Millipore, Carrigtwohill, Ireland) (first 0.45 µm, and then 0.22 µm). The bacteriophage titer was
107 determined by plating serial dilutions (1:10) onto LB plates using the double agar layer method (33).
108 When high titers of bacteriophage lysates were required, 50 ml of *Salmonella* cultures in LB broth at
109 an initial OD₅₅₀ of 0.2 were prepared and incubated at 37°C with agitation until an OD₅₅₀ of 1 was
110 obtained. The cultures were then infected with the appropriate bacteriophage at an MOI of 0.01
111 PFU/CFU, and suspensions were incubated at 37°C for 12 h to 14 h (33). Finally, the lysates were

112 recovered as described above. The bacteriophage lysates were concentrated by ultracentrifugation
113 (Optima™ L-80, Beckman, California, USA) in an 80Ti rotor (Beckman, California, USA) at 4°C
114 (68,584 X g for 2 h) (34). The pellets were resuspended in aqueous MgSO₄ (10 mM, pH 6.1) with
115 overnight shaking. The resulting bacteriophage suspensions were filtered through 0.45 µm PES
116 filters, and then stored at 4°C. The bacteriophage titer was determined as described above.

117 **Encapsulation method.**

118 The bacteriophages were encapsulated in lipids using the thin-film hydration method. A lipid
119 mixture of 1,2-dilauroyl-rac-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DLPC), cholesteryl polyethylene glycol 600
120 sebacate (cholesterol-PEG600), cholesterol (Chol) and cholesteryl 3β-N
121 (dimethylaminoethyl)carbamate hydrochloride (cholesteryl) was used (1:0.1:0.2:0.7 molar ratio).
122 Briefly, each lipid was dissolved in chloroform (100 mg/ml), and then 106 µl of DLPC, 17 µl of
123 cholesterol-PEG600, 13 µL of Chol and 64 µl of cholesteryl solutions were mixed under sterile
124 conditions. The total lipid concentration was 17 mM. The organic solvent was then removed under
125 vacuum and nitrogen to afford a dry lipid film. This film was hydrated with 2 ml of the appropriate
126 bacteriophage (either UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 or UAB_Phi87) at a concentration of 10¹¹ PFU/ml
127 under stirring for 1 h. At this point, stacks of liquid crystalline lipid bilayer became fluid and swell,
128 and the hydrated lipid sheets detached during agitation and self-closed to form large multilamellar
129 vesicles (LMV). The resulting LMV suspension was then homogenized (downsized) using an
130 extruder (Lipex Biomembranes, Vancouver, Canada) and a polycarbonate membrane (pore size: 400
131 nm) to obtain unilamellar vesicles. Particle-size distributions of the samples were determined using
132 a dynamic light scattering (DLS) analyser combined with non-invasive backscatter technology
133 (NIBS; Malvern Zetasizer, Malvern Instruments, U.K.). The samples (1 ml) were measured without
134 dilution, directly just after the preparation of the dispersed system. The mean values of three
135 different measurements were taken as the mean diameter. The stability of the liposome-encapsulated

136 bacteriophages was examined by means of the measurement of the zeta potential (ζ). These
137 measurements were performed by an electrophoretic mobility and light scattering analyser (Malvern
138 Zetasizer). Samples were placed into the potential cuvette and measured without dilution, just after
139 their preparation. The mean values of three different experiments were taken as the mean zeta
140 potential value of the dispersed system.

141 **Encapsulation efficiency.**

142 The efficiency with which the bacteriophages had been encapsulated (EE) was calculated according
143 to the following equation: $EE(\%) = 100 - (C_{\text{free}}/C_{\text{total}}) \times 100$, where C_{total} is the total bacteriophage
144 concentration and C_{free} is the concentration of free bacteriophages. To quantify C_{total} , 0.5 ml of
145 liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages were treated with 0.5 ml of bile salts (50 mM; Sigma-
146 Aldrich, Missouri, USA) to disrupt the liposomes. Previously, it was checked that this concentration
147 did not affect significantly the infectivity of bacteriophages. Afterwards, appropriate dilutions were
148 plated onto LB plates with LB5000 strain using the double agar layer method, and the C_{total} was
149 determined. To quantify C_{free} , liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages were directly titered by plating
150 serial dilutions (1:10) with LB5000 tester strain. Encapsulation efficiencies were also determined for
151 the samples that had been stored at 4°C for 3 months, following the methodology described above.

152 **Microscopy.**

153 Liposome integrity (morphology and lamellarity) was examined using cryogenic transmission
154 electron microscopy (cryo-TEM) in a JEOL-JEM 1400 microscope (JEOL Ltd., Japan). Samples
155 were prepared in a controlled environment vitrification system. A 5 μl sample was placed on a
156 carbon-coated holey film supported by a standard copper TEM grid. After 30 s, the grid was gently
157 blotted with a double layer of filter paper to obtain a thin film (thickness: 20 nm to 400 nm),
158 plunged into liquid ethane at its freezing point (-180°C), and finally, transferred into liquid nitrogen

159 (-196°C). The vitrified specimens were stored in liquid nitrogen, and then transferred to a
160 microscope using a cryotransfer and its workstation (Gatan 626 DH, Gatan).

161 To confirm that the bacteriophages had indeed been encapsulated into liposomes, fluorescently-
162 labeled samples were prepared, and then observed by laser confocal microscopy using a Leica TCS
163 SP5 confocal microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany). Bacteriophages were stained with
164 SYBR-gold (Molecular Probes, Oregon, USA) 100x by adding 0.02 ml of SYBR-gold to 10 ml of
165 bacteriophages at 10^{11} PFU/ml suspended in MgSO_4 10 mM, and incubated in darkness overnight
166 (35). Subsequently, the samples were ultra-filtered and washed (3 times at 5,000 X g) using Amicon
167 ultra 50K tubes (Millipore, Carrigtwohill, Ireland). The fluorescent SYBR-gold-labeled
168 bacteriophages were encapsulated using the thin-film hydration method described above, with the
169 DLPC/Cholesteryl/Chol/Chol-PEG lipid mixture incorporating the Vibrant DiI phospholipid-
170 labeling solution (10 μ L Vibrant DiI per 20 mg lipid). In this case the liposomes were not extruded,
171 due to the resolution limit of the optical microscope. A 30 μ l sample was placed on a coated glass
172 slide and observed in resonance scanning mode.

173 **Lyophilization.**

174 For long-term conservation of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages, the cryoprotectant
175 trehalose was added during the liposome synthesis and the encapsulated bacteriophages were
176 subjected to freeze-drying lyophilization. In this case, the dry lipid film was hydrated with a
177 suspension containing the bacteriophages and trehalose at a lipid/carbohydrate ratio of 1:5 (3.2%
178 w/v). The resulting cryo-protected liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages were frozen at -80°C for 2
179 h and lyophilized at -40°C for 48 h. For comparison, non-encapsulated bacteriophages were also
180 lyophilized with the cryoprotectant trehalose. When needed, the lyophilized samples were re-
181 suspended in aqueous MgSO_4 (10 mM) and plated as indicated above to determine the pre- and
182 post-lyophilization bacteriophage titer for use in calculating the bacteriophage infectivity.

183 **Bacteriophage stability in simulated gastric fluid.**

184 The liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages were tested for stability to simulated gastric fluid
185 solution (pH 2.8) comprising pepsin (3 mg/ml, Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA) in NaCl 0.85 (36).
186 In all cases, 0.1 ml of encapsulated bacteriophages were added to 10 ml of the simulated gastric
187 fluid solution. No change of the value of pH was observed. Samples were then incubated in a water
188 bath at 42°C with agitation to mimic avian stomach conditions. To determinate the total
189 bacteriophage concentration, aliquots were taken at 0 min, 30 min and 60 min, treated with bile salts
190 (50 mM), and plated as previously described. The same methodology was employed to test non-
191 encapsulated bacteriophages, but without the bile salt treatment.

192 ***In vivo* assays in broilers.**

193 The intestinal residence time and the bacteriophage therapy effectiveness against *Salmonella* of
194 liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages (cocktail) and of non-encapsulated bacteriophages (cocktail)
195 were evaluated *in vivo* in commercial broilers (*Gallus gallus*, Ross strain 308; Terra-Avant S.A.,
196 Girona, Spain). The animals were treated in agreement with the guidelines of the appropriate ethics
197 commission [Comissió d'Ètica en l'Experimentació Animal i Humana (CEEAH)] at our host
198 institution, the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB). The Commission approved our study
199 under authorization number 1953.

200 Newly hatched chickens were purchased and subsequently transported to a biosafety level 2 animal-
201 testing facility at the UAB' Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals (Cerdanyola del Vallès,
202 Spain). Broilers were housed in farmyards with food and water supplied *ad libitum*. In an attempt to
203 simulate farm conditions and increase the feeding impulse of the animals, the animals were kept
204 under 23 h/1 h light/dark cycles using green and blue light (37). Before any experiment, two
205 chickens were sacrificed to confirm that they were free of *Salmonella* and of bacteriophages,
206 following enrichment protocols. For detection of *Salmonella*, homogenized tissues were incubated

207 in buffered peptone water (BPW; Merck) at 37°C for 18 h. Next, 0.2 ml of tissue suspension were
208 inoculated in 2 ml of Müller-Kauffman selective broth (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and incubated
209 at 37°C for 24 h. Then, 0.1 ml of this culture was plated onto XLD plates. Bacteriophages were
210 detected as previously reported (10). Briefly, 0.2 ml of these homogenates were added to cultures of
211 2 ml of *Salmonella* Typhimurium in LB at optical density (OD_{550 nm}) of 0.2, and incubated at 37°C
212 for 24 h. The presence of bacteriophages was determined by spotting 10 µL of the above-described
213 suspensions onto lawns of *S. Typhimurium* ATCC Rif^R. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h,
214 and bacterial lysis was observed.

215 The *in vivo* assays were based on oral administration of either 100 µl liposome-encapsulated
216 bacteriophage cocktail or 100 µl non-encapsulated bacteriophage cocktail to the broilers. The
217 cocktail comprised a 1:1:1 mixture of the bacteriophages UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 and UAB_Phi87
218 at a concentration of 10¹¹ PFU/ml in MgSO₄ buffer without any antacid. All oral inoculations were
219 performed using a curved oral-dosing needle (75 mm; 16G, Veterinary instrumentation, Sheffield,
220 UK).

221 ***In vivo* retention in the intestinal tract.**

222 The intestinal residence time of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophage cocktail and of the non-
223 encapsulated bacteriophage cocktail was determined over 72 h. To this end, two groups of 63 1-day-
224 old chickens were housed on two poultry farmyards. One group was treated with liposome-
225 encapsulated bacteriophage cocktail; and the other group, with the non-encapsulated bacteriophage
226 cocktail. In both cases the dose was 10¹⁰ PFU/animal. One hundred µl were orally administered at 0
227 h, and 21 animals from each group were euthanized at 2 h, 48 h and 72 h. Upon euthanasia, animals
228 were necropsied and samples of their cecum were taken. For bacteriophage quantification, serial
229 dilutions of homogenized cecum samples were plated onto a lawn of *Salmonella* Typhimurium
230 ATCC Rif^R using the double agar layer method, and then were incubated at 37°C for 24 h. When

231 direct detection of bacteriophages was not possible, the enrichment procedure was done, as detailed
232 above.

233 **Bacteriophage therapy efficacy assay.**

234 The bacteriophage therapy assay was based on oral administration of 100 µl of a solution of
235 liposome-encapsulated bacteriophage cocktail or non-encapsulated bacteriophage cocktail. The
236 efficacy of each treatment against *Salmonella* was assessed over 17 days. The animals were orally
237 infected with 100 µl of a suspension of *S. Typhimurium* ATCC14028 Rif^R in LB medium at a dose
238 of 10⁷ CFU/animal on day 0. Three groups of 84 recently-hatched commercial broilers (*Gallus*
239 *gallus*, Ross strain 308) were separated in farmyards. The first group was the control group for
240 *Salmonella* colonization and did not receive any treatment. The second group (non-encapsulated
241 group) received the non-encapsulated bacteriophages and the third group (encapsulated group), the
242 encapsulated bacteriophages. Both treatments were administered once daily orally (10¹⁰
243 PFU/animal), from day -1 to day 7 post-infection with *Salmonella*. The control group was orally
244 inoculated on the same days with an aqueous suspension of MgSO₄ (10 mM). In each group, 14
245 chickens were euthanized on days 1, 3, 6, 8, 10, and 15 post-infection, and cecum samples were
246 obtained for *Salmonella* quantification. To count *Salmonella*, the tissues were weighed, resuspended
247 in 4 ml of BPW, and then mechanically homogenized for 15 min. Serial dilutions of the
248 homogenates were prepared and plated on XLD agar plates (Laboratorios Conda, Spain)
249 supplemented with rifampicin (75 µg/ml). After incubation, colonies of *Salmonella* were recorded.
250 For each treatment, bacterial reduction was calculated by subtracting the mean cecal concentration
251 of bacteria (expressed in log units) of either treated group from the mean value of the Control group.

252 ***In vitro* studies of bacteriophage release.**

253 The release of bacteriophages from liposomes promoted by the cecum content was studied. Twelve
254 1-day-old chickens were maintained during 15 days in farmyards as explained above. Animals were

255 euthanized, and the content of ceca was obtained. For each bacteriophage, 990 μ l of content ceca
256 were mixed with 10 μ l of liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages, and incubated at 42°C because it is
257 the body temperature of chickens. The concentration of bacteriophages was determined along the
258 time by plating the appropriately dilutions using the double agar layer method.

259 **Statistical analysis.**

260 All results obtained were analyzed using IBM SPSS software. For normal distribution samples
261 ANOVA and the T-student test were applied, whereas in cases of non-normal distribution, the
262 Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney tests were used. The polydispersity index (PdI) which is the
263 square of the standard deviation / mean diameter was determined as a measure of the width of the
264 particle size distribution

265 **RESULTS**

266 **Characterization of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages.**

267 Each lytic bacteriophage (UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 or UAB_Ph87) (18, 19) was separately
268 encapsulated into liposomes. Cationic liposomes comprising 1,2-dilauroyl-rac-glycero-3-
269 phosphocholine (DLPC), 3 β -N-(dimethylaminoethyl)carbamate hydrochloride (Cholesteryl),
270 cholesterol (Chol) and cholesteryl-polyethylene glycol 600 sebacate (Chol-PEG600) were prepared
271 through the method of thin-film hydration (38). Encapsulation began with hydration of a dry lipid
272 film with an aqueous magnesium sulfate suspension containing the bacteriophages. Then, the
273 resulting mixture was extruded through a 400-nm polycarbonate membrane and liposome-
274 encapsulated bacteriophages were characterized.

275 DLS indicated that the sizes of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages were 308.6 ± 20.9 nm for
276 UAB_Phi20 (PdI = 0.14), 320.6 ± 15.2 nm for UAB_Phi78 (PdI = 0.21) and 325.8 ± 23.1 nm for
277 UAB_Phi87 (PdI=0.18) (Fig. 1). Zeta-potential (ζ potential) measurements revealed that the surface

278 charges of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages were $+35.1 \pm 1.0$ mV for UAB_Phi20, $+33.0 \pm$
279 2.1 mV for UAB_Phi78 and $+31.6 \pm 1.3$ mV for UAB_Phi87 (Table 1).

280 The morphology and structure of the resulting liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages were imaged
281 by cryogenic transmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM). As shown in Figures 2A-C, individual
282 bacteriophages were encapsulated into unilamellar liposomes, in which the number of encapsulated
283 bacteriophages in a single liposome varied. Some empty liposomes and non-encapsulated
284 bacteriophages were observed, most of which were attached to the external surface of the liposome.
285 The sizes of the liposomes determined by cryo-TEM were consistent with those observed by DLS.
286 Encapsulation efficiency for each bacteriophage was determined by preparing six independent
287 encapsulation batches. The encapsulation yields (expressed as a percentage) achieved were $49 \pm$
288 2.4% for UAB_Phi20, $48 \pm 6.4\%$ for UAB_Phi78, and $47 \pm 5.1\%$ for UAB_Phi87 (Table 1). To
289 further characterize the physicochemical structure of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages, we
290 encapsulated the corresponding SYBR gold-labeled bacteriophage into Dil-labeled liposomes.
291 Figures 2D-F show the 3D spatial superimposition of the fluorescence intensities of SYBR gold-
292 labeled UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 or UAB_Phi87 bacteriophages (in green) and those of the Dil-
293 labeled liposomes (in red). The images confirmed that each type of bacteriophage had indeed been
294 encapsulated inside the liposomes.

295 Following, the stability of each encapsulated bacteriophage (*i.e.* the extent to which the
296 bacteriophages remained inside the liposome) was tested. To this end, freshly encapsulated
297 bacteriophages were characterized by DLS, by zeta-potential measurements and the concentration of
298 liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages was also determined. Next, samples of each freshly
299 encapsulated bacteriophage were stored at 4°C for 3 months, and subsequently characterized as
300 above. Encouragingly, no significant differences were found for any of the parameter values

301 between the fresh and stored encapsulated bacteriophages (Table 1), thereby confirming the stability
302 of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages under the test conditions (4 °C and 3 months).

303 **Lyophilization of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages.**

304 With the purpose to obtain a stable product suitable for long-term storage and with an easy way to
305 administrate to animal water or feed in future, we determined the effect of the lyophilization
306 procedure on liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages. Previously to lyophilization, the cryoprotectant
307 trehalose (24) was added to the suspension containing the bacteriophages during the synthetic
308 hydration step. Likewise, non-encapsulated bacteriophages were also lyophilized for comparison
309 purpose. After lyophilization, each resulting dry powder was reconstituted by re-suspension in
310 aqueous magnesium sulfate, and the titer of bacteriophages was determined. Table 2 shows the
311 percentage of the titer of both non-encapsulated and encapsulated bacteriophages after lyophilization
312 with respect to their titer before lyophilization. All the encapsulated bacteriophages exhibited much
313 higher values than did the corresponding non-encapsulated ones ($p < 0.05$). The encapsulated
314 bacteriophages UAB-Phi20 and UAB-Phi87 exhibited values of roughly 82% and 84% whereas the
315 non-encapsulated ones showed values of only 22% and 47%, respectively. Furthermore, albeit the
316 UAB_Phi78 bacteriophage was drastically more sensitive to lyophilization than were the
317 UAB_Phi20 or UAB_Phi87 bacteriophages, the difference in the post-lyophilization percentage
318 between the encapsulated and non-encapsulated forms was the greatest for this bacteriophage (15%
319 for encapsulated vs. 2% for non-encapsulated; a difference of seven times).

320 **Bacteriophage resistance to simulated gastric fluids.**

321 The acid stability of liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages and the non-encapsulated ones was
322 tested in simulated gastric fluid (SGF) at pH 2.8 for 60 min. The non-encapsulated bacteriophages
323 were all sensitive to this condition (Fig. 3). In this sense, by 30 min incubation all the
324 bacteriophages had begun to be affected, as indicated by titer losses of 4.2 log units (UAB_Phi20),

325 6.2 log units (UAB_Phi78) and 6.1 log units (UAB_Phi87). By 60 min incubation, the titer values
326 continued decreasing, with losses of 5.7 log units (UAB_Phi20), 8.0 log units (UAB_Phi78) and 7.8
327 log units (UAB_Phi87). In contrast, all three encapsulated bacteriophages were less prone to acidic
328 degradation than were the corresponding non-encapsulated ones: at both time points measured, the
329 loss in titer was less severe for the former than for the latter (Fig. 3, $p < 0.05$). Thus, after 30 min of
330 incubation, the losses in titer for the encapsulated bacteriophages were 3.2 log units (UAB_Phi20),
331 4.0 log units (UAB_Phi78) and 3.3 log units (UAB_Phi87). After 60 minutes incubation, the losses
332 in titer for the encapsulated bacteriophages were 4.8 log units (UAB_Phi20), 5.4 log units
333 (UAB_Phi78) and 3.7 log units (UAB_Phi87).

334 ***In vivo* retention in the intestinal tract.**

335 Next, we determined whether cationic liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages UAB_Phi20,
336 UAB_Phi78 or UAB_Phi87 would exhibit longer intestinal residence time *in vivo* in broilers than
337 would the non-encapsulated ones. We prepared two bacteriophage cocktails: one comprising a 1:1:1
338 mixture of the three liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages, and one comprising a 1:1:1 mixture of
339 the three non-encapsulated bacteriophages. In both cases the final concentration was 10^{11} PFU/ml.
340 Then, we studied two groups of 63 broilers: one that was treated with the first cocktail (encapsulated
341 group); and one that was treated with the second cocktail other group (non-encapsulated group). For
342 each group, 21 chickens were euthanized after 2 h, 48 h and 72 h of cocktail administration, and the
343 presence of bacteriophages in the cecum of each animal was determined after sacrifice. Figure 4
344 shows the percentage of chickens from each treatment group that contained bacteriophages in the
345 cecum at each of the three time points tested. After 2 h, no significant differences in the percentage
346 of chickens containing bacteriophages were observed (66.7% of the encapsulated group vs. 57.1% of
347 the non-encapsulated group). However, significant differences arose after 48 h (90.5% of the

348 encapsulated vs. 38.1% of the non-encapsulated, $p < 0.001$) and after 72 h (38.1% of the
349 encapsulated vs. 9.5% of the non-encapsulated, $p < 0.05$).

350 **Bacteriophage therapy against *Salmonella*.**

351 The efficacy of bacteriophage therapy of each of the above cocktails (encapsulated vs. non-
352 encapsulated) against *Salmonella* colonization in commercial broilers was tested. Table 3 shows the
353 *Salmonella* concentration in the cecum of the chickens from each group, revealing that the two
354 treated groups had lower levels of this bacterium than did the control group. Results indicate that the
355 two cocktails had different long-term efficacies against *Salmonella* infection in the cecum. Within
356 the first 6 days post-infection (the period during which the two treated groups received their
357 respective cocktails), the two treated groups exhibited similar and significant drops in *Salmonella*
358 concentration. However, by the first day on which no treatment was given (day 8), the difference in
359 the decrease between the *Salmonella* concentration in the non-encapsulated group and the control
360 group was only significant on this day (reduction of 1.5 log₁₀; $p < 0.05$); contrariwise, the difference
361 between the encapsulated group and the control group was significant until the end of the
362 experiment (day 15; $p < 0.001$). For example, the reductions at days 8, 10 and 15 were 3.8 log unit,
363 3.9 log unit and 1.5 log unit, respectively. Furthermore, we would like to highlight that when the
364 two treatments were statistically compared for efficacy, the encapsulated bacteriophages showed a
365 statistically significantly greater reduction in *Salmonella* from day 8 ($p < 0.05$) until the end of the
366 experiment (day 15; $p < 0.001$).

367 ***In vitro* bacteriophage release by cecum content.**

368 The release of liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages mediated by cecum content was evaluated by
369 incubating the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages with the cecum content for 60 min. After 30
370 min the percentage of release of bacteriophages UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 and UAB_Phi87 was

371 19.4 ± 2.6 , 80 ± 17.2 and 42.7 ± 14.1 , respectively (Fig. 5). This values were 74.7 ± 5.4 , 92.6 ± 12.4
372 and 56.6 ± 16.7 , respectively after 60 min (Fig. 5).

373

374 **DISCUSSION**

375 With the objective to overcome the problems inherent in oral application of bacteriophages to
376 control bacterial pathogens, bacteriophages were encapsulated in liposomes. We reasoned that
377 cationic liposomal complexes of bacteriophages would promote the release of the bacteriophage in
378 the target area and permit their activity against *Salmonella*.

379 Our data showed that the proposed method of encapsulation using the designed lipid mixture allows
380 the encapsulation of the three targeted bacteriophages (UAB_Phi20, UAB_Phi78 and UAB_Ph87)
381 in cationic lipid envelopes with efficiencies nearly to 50%. It must be noted that the encapsulation
382 procedure described here do not inactive the bacteriophages and it can be used for bacteriophage
383 with different morphologies. Thus, bacteriophages UAB_Phi20 and UAB_Phi78 have an
384 icosahedral head (60 ± 1.5 nm and 66 ± 1.7 nm, respectively) and a non-contractile short tail ($13 \pm$
385 0.7 nm and 14 ± 0.7 nm, respectively) and UAB_Phi87 has an icosahedral head (68 ± 2.7 nm) but a
386 long, contractile tail (114 ± 4.3 nm) (20, 21).

387 A first obvious advantage of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages is that they are stable in
388 aqueous suspensions at 4°C for at least 3 months. In addition, they can be transformed into a dry,
389 stable powder that can be suitable for long-term storage. Different studies report that lyophilizing
390 bacteriophages-even encapsulated ones-comprises their lytic activity. For example, alginate-
391 chitosan-encapsulated and PLGA-encapsulated bacteriophages have each been reported to suffer this
392 fate (24, 39). In contrast, in a study on lyophilization of non-encapsulated dysentery bacteriophage,
393 in which raw egg yolk was employed as a source of phospholipids, the bacteriophage survived
394 lyophilization (34). In our case, the significant lower susceptibility of the encapsulated

395 bacteriophages to the lyophilization process in comparison with the non-encapsulated ones can be
396 attributed to the lipid mixture combined with the addition of the cryoprotectant trehalose.

397 As it was hypothesized, the cationic lipids used in the lipid mixture offer a barrier to protons to
398 orally administered bacteriophages during their transit through the stomach (pH *ca.* 1 to 3) because
399 the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages retain a high activity in simulated gastric conditions
400 compared to the non-encapsulated ones (Fig. 3). Moreover, data obtained after oral administration to
401 broilers of encapsulated bacteriophage cocktail indicate that the cationic liposome encapsulation
402 enables a significantly higher intestinal residence time of bacteriophages after 48 and 72 hours of
403 administration compared to the non-encapsulated (Fig. 4). Furthermore, and in agreement with their
404 resistance to gastric pH, the concentration of encapsulated bacteriophages in the cecum was
405 significant higher than that of the non-encapsulated ones after 2 h of their administration (data not
406 shown). In addition, as it was shown in *in vitro* experiments (Fig. 5), the content of cecum provokes
407 different kinetics of release of bacteriophages from liposomes which can be attributed to the distinct
408 affinity of proteins of capsids and tails for the lipids used to encapsulate them. We believe that this
409 effect would be mainly due to the bile salts present in the cecum content. These results indicate that
410 release must also be produced *in vivo*, because the intestinal tract of broilers contains the enough
411 concentration of bile salts to break the liposomes (36). However, the situation *in vivo* undoubtedly is
412 more complex and makes difficult a comparison with the release kinetics observed *in vitro*.

413 Different aspects as the adherence of liposomes to the intestinal mucosa, the mucus produced by the
414 underlying epithelium and the digestive process of food could slow down the release of
415 bacteriophages. All these facts are crucial for the success of the bacteriophage therapy because once
416 bacteriophages pass through the stomach they remain retained in the intestinal tract. In this sense, it
417 has been described that some bacteriophage can interact *in vitro* with tissue culture cells that contain
418 mucus (40). However, it was also reported that the concentration of bacteriophages in the gut

419 decreases dramatically when the bacterial host diminishes (20) and, consequently, they would be
420 retained in the mucous membrane for only a short time. Here, we show that a way to address the
421 inherently low retention of bacteriophages is to encapsulate them in matrices such as liposomes.
422 Researchers have reported that cationic liposomes exhibit mucoadhesive properties. Thus, positive
423 charge of the cationic liposome-encapsulated formulations of orally administered active species
424 offer much better permeability in the intestinal mucosa and much longer retention compared to the
425 non-encapsulated active species (28, 29).

426 Together, all the advantages conferred by the lipid mixture commented till now should enhance the
427 therapeutic effect of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages. Results about the efficacy of each of
428 the two bacteriophage cocktails (encapsulated *vs.* non-encapsulated) against *Salmonella* colonization
429 in commercial broilers show that the two cocktails had different long-term efficacies against
430 *Salmonella* infection in the cecum (Fig. 4). When administered daily for 6 days post-infection, the
431 two cocktails similarly protected the chickens against *Salmonella* colonization. However, once
432 treatment had been stopped, the protective effects of the non-encapsulated bacteriophages
433 disappeared after 72 hours. In contrast, the protective effects of the encapsulated bacteriophages
434 persisted for 1 week, consistently with their higher intestinal residence time and supporting the
435 notion that the bacteriophages are gradually released from the liposomes.

436 It is important to remember that the bacteriophage therapy study was done on chickens infected with
437 *Salmonella* (*i.e.* the bacteriophage host), whereas the *in vivo* intestinal retention study was done on
438 chickens without *Salmonella*. This difference is crucial to interpreting and comparing the results
439 from each study since, during treatment in infected animals, bacteriophages can multiplied as they
440 are released, thereby generating new progeny (41). This phenomenon might help to explain the
441 superior performance of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages in our bacteriophage therapy
442 study.

443 In summary, we show that bacteriophages with different morphologies can be encapsulated into
444 cationic liposomes, and are markedly more stable to acid and to lyophilization *in vitro* than the
445 corresponding non-encapsulated bacteriophages. It is noteworthy that the nanometric size of the
446 liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages confers excellent characteristics for their real applications.
447 For example, their nanometric size avoids their sedimentation in drinking water, which would be the
448 preferred administration way, and makes possible their mixing with the grind feed usually
449 administered to younger broilers as well as their addition to the pellet for older chickens after the
450 pelletizing process without compromising the quality of the feed. We have also demonstrated that
451 the encapsulated bacteriophages exhibit longer intestinal residence time *in vivo*, in commercial
452 broilers and the bacteriophages are delivered from liposomes in the intestinal tract. These
453 characteristics enable the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages to have stronger and longer-lasting
454 therapeutic effects at fighting *Salmonella* infection in the digestive tract of such chickens. We are
455 confident that our findings will help researchers to overcome some of the disadvantages of oral
456 bacteriophage therapy against other bacterial pathogens.

457

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466

467

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- 577

578 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

579 **Fig. 1.** (A) Schematic representation of the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophage system, showing
580 the presence of bacteriophages (green) encapsulated inside the liposome or attached to the liposome
581 external surface. (B-D) Particle-size distribution plots for the liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages
582 of UAB_Phi20 (B), UAB_Phi78 (C) and UAB_Phi87 (D), as measured by dynamic light scattering
583 (DLS).

584 **Fig. 2.** Cryo-TEM images of liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages: (A) UAB_Phi20, (B)
585 UAB_Phi78 and (C) UAB_Phi87 bacteriophages. 3D confocal microscopy images of SYBR gold-
586 labeled bacteriophages (green) encapsulated into fluorescent Dil-labeled liposomes (red):
587 UAB_Phi20 (D), UAB_Phi78 (E) and UAB_Phi87 (F) bacteriophages. For (D-F): left: 3D images of
588 the liposome surface; right: the corresponding cross-sectional images; scale bars are 5 μm .

589 **Fig. 3.** Stability of non-encapsulated (white) and liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages (gray) in
590 simulated gastric fluid (pH 2.8). (A) UAB_Phi20; (B) UAB_Phi78 and (C) UAB_Phi87. Each value
591 is the average of six independent experiments \pm standard error. *, $p < 0.05$.

592 **Fig. 4.** Persistence of non-encapsulated (white) and liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages (gray) in
593 the cecum of broilers. *, $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$.

594 **Fig. 5.** *In vitro* release of liposome-encapsulated bacteriophages (gray) in contact with cecum
595 content (X) UAB_Phi20; (XX) UAB_Phi78 and (EE) UAB_Phi87. Each value is the average of six
596 independent experiments \pm standard error.

597